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Review Article

Comprehensive Review On Analytical Methods For Determination Of Chlorpheniramine Maleate In Pharmaceutical Dosage Form And Bulk

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ABSTRACT

The specified paper present a systematic review conduct on different methods for the analysis o the antihistamine drug. The focus of the article I to verify how the validation process of an analytical method I performed. Chlorpheniramine is approved by the U.S. Food and Drug administration is safe and effective when used to antihistamine and allergies. It is a prescription medication ues to preventing the release of histamine by acts on the brain and relieves symptoms of allergies. To provide relief form allergies symptoms such as sneezing, running nose, watery eyes, itching, swelling, and congestion or stiffness. Most recent analytical methods such as various spectroscopic methods (simultaneous estimation, Q absorption ratio) and chromatographic methods (RP-HPLC, HPTLC, LC) are included in review. In different articles, the study is conducted on various analytical parameters such as mobile phase, the ratio of mobile phase, stationary phase, flow rate, wavelength ect. The observation are made based on Retention time, Area of peak, peak height, therotical plates, AUC, ect. From the data found in the literature, a comparison is made between different methods and observation

INTRODUCTION

Drug analysis plays a significant role in drug development, manufacturing, and its therapeutic use. Allergies are Immunological diseases caused by hypersensitivity reaction with external agents like allergens present in the environment. It works by blocking the action of histamine, a substance in the body that causes allergic symptoms such as watery eyes, runny nose, sneezing. The

psychomotor stimulant effects of chlorpheniramine involve action other than the blockade of histamine H1 and H2 receptors. H1 Receptor antagonist indicated for the management of symptoms associated with upper respiratory allergies. Chlorpheniramine maleate appears white crystalline solid or white powder with bitter taste.

Molecular weight	390.864 g/mol
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State	Solid.
Taste	bitter
Chemical name	(Z)-but-2-enedioic acid ; 3-(4-chlorophenyl)-N,N-dimethylpyridin-2 Ylpropan-1-amine
Category	Antihistamine, Antiallergic
Solubility	Freely soluble in water, soluble in alcohol and in chloroform, slightly soluble in ether and benzene.
Description	Odorless, White crystalline solid or white powder, Bitter taste.
Ph	4.0 & 5.5
Storage	Store at room temperature , protected from light, Keep container
Melting point	266-2750C
Wavelength	262nm

Fig 1: Chlorpheniramine Maleate

ANALYTICAL METHODS

The Analytical methods which are used for the determination of the chlorpheniramine maleate in the marketed formulation and in bulk are identified during the literature survey and reported. The present article describes the review on the analytical methods with specific conditions.

1. Chromatographic Methods

Various chromatographic methods are used for the determination of the chlorpheniramine maleate in combination with other drugs or alone in various marketed formulations. Chromatographic methods like Reverse phase High-performance liquid chromatography (RP-HPLC), High-performance thin-layer chromatography (HPTLC), and Ultra performance liquid chromatography (UPLC) are used for the determination of Chlorpheniramine maleate.

The given table describe the summary of the various chromatographic methods with the method description.

Table No. 1: Chromatographic methods of Chlorpheniramine maleate

Sr No.	Title	Method	Mobile Phase and Flow Rate	Column	Retention time and wavelength	Ref No.
1.	Development and Validation of RP-HPLC Method for simultaneous estimation of chlorpheniramine maleate and Diethylcarbamazine citrate in pharmaceutical dosage forms.	RP-HPLC	Acetonitrile:Potassium dihydrogen phosphate (80:20 v/v) Flow rate: 1.0ml/min	Kromasil C ₁₈ Column (250mmX4.6 mm) 5µm	RT: CPM:4.042min Diethylcrbamazin e-2.808min 238nm	4
2.	RP-HPLC-DAD method for the determination of Phenylephrine, paracetamol, caffeine and chlorpheniramine in bulk and marketed formulation.	RP-HPLC-DAD	Acetonitrile:Methanol:10 Mm phosphate buffer (16:22:62 v/v/v) Flow rate: 1.0ml/min	C ₁₈ Column (150mmX4.5 mm) 5µm	RT: CPM-10.9min PE-1.8min Para-3.1min Caffeine- 5.2min 280nm	5

3.	Validated RP-HPLC method for simultaneous determination and quantification of chlorpheniramine maleate, paracetamol, caffeine in tablet formulation.	RP-HPLC	Methanol: Phosphate buffer (30:70 v/v) Flow rate: 1.0ml/min	Phenomenex C ₁₈ Column (250 X 4.6mm) Luna 5µm	RT: CPM:2.4min Paracetamol:4.2min in Caffeine:7.2min 215nm	6
4.	A chromatographic method for rapid and simultaneous analysis of codeine phosphate, ephedrine HCL and chlorpheniramine maleate in cough-cold syrup formulation.	HPLC	1.Methanol: glacial acetic acid: trimethylamine (980:15:6 v/v/v) 2.Water: glacial acetic acid: trimethylamine (980:15:6 v/v/v) Flow rate: 1.5ml/min	Zorbax XBD C ₈ Column(150 X4.6mm) 5µm	RT: CPM:6.78min CP:2.27min EP: 3.23min 254nm	7
5.	Simultaneous determination of paracetamol, phenylephrine HCL, Oxalamide citrate and chlorpheniramine maleate by HPLC in pharmaceutical dosage forms.	HPLC	0.02M Phosphate buffer:Acetonitrile (85:15 v/v) Flow rate: 1.5ml/min	Zorbax SB-CN Column (150X4.6m) 5µm	RT: CPM:3.34 min Paracetamol:1.18 min Phenylephrine HCL:2.18min Oxolamine citrate:2.80min 365nm	8
6.	Stability-indicating High Performance liquid chromatography method for simultaneous determination of Aminophylline and chlorpheniramine maleate in pharmaceutical formulations.	RP-HPLC	Dilute H ₂ SO ₄ :Methanol (60:40 v/v) Flow rate: 1.5ml/min	C ₁₈ Column (250 X 4.6mm) 5µm	RT: CPM:3.25 min Aminophylline:2.00min 264nm	10
7.	Simultaneous estimation of paracetamol, Guaiphenesin, phenylephrine HCL, chlorpheniramine maleate and bromhexine HCL in combined tablet dosage form by	RP-HPLC	Methanol:Acetonitrile (3:2 v/v) Flow rate: 1.0ml/min	Symmetry C ₈ Column (150 X 4.6mm) 3.5µm	RT: CPM:21.78min Paracetamol:5.73 min Guaiphenesin:17.46min Phenylephrine HCL:18.29 min Bromhexine HCL:2355min	11

	reverse phase High performance Liquid chromatography.				220nm	
8.	Validated stability-indicating RP-HPLC method for simultaneous Estimation of codeine phosphate and chlorpheniramine maleate from their combined liquid dosage form.	RP-HPLC	Water:Acetonitrile:Methanol (78:10:12 v/v/v) Flow rate: 1.0ml/min	Phenomenex C ₁₈ Column (250 X 4.6mm) 5µm	RT: CPM:9.45 min Codeine Phosphate:3.47 min 254nm	12
9.	Development and validation of RP-HPLC method for simultaneous estimation of Nimesulide, Phenylephrine HCL, chlorpheniramine maleate, Caffeine Anhydrous in pharmaceutical dosage form.	RP-HPLC	Methanol: Buffer (55.45 v/v) Flow rate: 1.0ml/min	Hypersil phenyl column (4.6mmX25 cm)	RT: CPM:17.15min NS:7.47min PE:3.944min CF:4.55min 214nm	13
10	Development and validation of RP-HPLC method for simultaneous estimation of Diethylcarbamazine citrate and chlorpheniramine maleate in pharmaceutical preparation	RP-HPLC	Methanol: Buffer (55.45 v/v) Flow rate: 1.0ml/min	Hypersil ODS C ₁₈ (250 X4.6mm) 5µm	RT: CPM:2.091min Diethylcarbamazine citrate:4.74min 254nm	14
11	A novel HPLC method for the simultaneous determination of chlorpheniramine maleate and Dextromethorphan in bulk and pharmaceutical formulation.	HPLC	Water: Acetonitrile (60:40 v/v) Flow rate: 1.0ml/min	Discovery C ₁₈ Column (250mmX4.6 mm) 5µm	RT: CPM:3.0min Dextromethorphan:3.6min 218nm	15
12	Development and validation of an RP-HPLC method for estimation of chlorpheniramine	RP-HPLC	Acetonitrile:Methanol:Phosphat buffer (50:20:30 v/v/v)	Sunfire C ₁₈ Column (250mmX4.6 mm)	RT: CPM: 4.2min IBU:13.6min PHE:2.7 min	16

	maleate, Ibuprofen, and phenylephrine hydrochloride in combined pharmaceutical dosage form.		Flow rate: 1.0ml/min	5µm	220nm	
13	Stability indicating RP-HPLC method development and validation of paracetamol, Guaifenesin, Ambroxol hydrochloride, phenylephrine hydrochloride and chlorpheniramine maleate in bulk and combined dosage form.	RP-HPLC	Buffer: Acetonitrile (50:50 v/v) Flow rate: 1.5ml/min	Zodiac C ₁₈ (50mmX4.6 mm) 5µm	RT: CPM: 7.319 min Paracetamol:3.99 3Mmin Phenylephrine HCL: 4.450 min Amroxol HCL:6.0min Guaifenesin:6.869 min 225nm	17
14	Validated RP-HPLC method for determining the levels of bromhexine hydrochloride, chlorpheniramine maleate, dextromethorphan HBr and Guaiphenesin in their pharmaceutical dosage form	RP-HPLC	Methanol:Acetonitrile: Phosphate buffer (50:25:25 v/v/v) Flow rate: 1.0ml/min	Chromatopak C ₁₈ (25cm x 4.6mm) 5µm	RT: CPM:12.21 min Bromhexine Hcl:16.25 min Dextromethorphan HCL: 6.15 min Guaiphenesin: 9.43min 265nm	18
15	Simultaneous High performance Liquid Chromatography determination of paracetamol, Phenylephrine hydrochloride and chlorpheniramine maleate in pharmaceutical dosage form	HPLC	Acetonitrile: Phosphate Buffer (78:22 v/v) Flow rate: 1.5ml/min	uBondapak CN RP Analytical Column (3.9 X 150mm) 10µm	RT: CPM: 3.44min Paracetamol:1.13 min Phenylephrine HCL:2.13min 265nm	3
16	Development and validation of RP-HPLC method for the determination of chlorpheniramine maleate and phenylephrine in pharmaceutical dosage form	RP-HPLC	Acetonitrile: Phosphate Buffer (55:45 v/v) Flow rate: 1.0ml/min	C ₁₈ Column (250mmX8m m) 10µm	RT: CPM: 3.13 min Phenylephrine: 4.58min 255nm	19

17	Simultaneous determination of chlorpheniramine maleate and Dexamethasone in a tablet dosage form by liquid chromatography	LC	7.5Mm monobasic potassium phosphate in Methanol:water (62.5 + 37.5) Flow rate: 1.0ml/min	C ₁₈ Column (250 X 4.6mm) 10µm	RT: CPM:5min Dexamethaone:11 min 254nm	9
18	Assessment of the greenness of micellar HPLC method for rapid separation and simultaneous estimation of chlorpheniramine maleate in presence of some co-administered drug (Levocloperatinefen dizoate, Dextromethorphan hydrobromide, Dexamethasone) in three pharmaceutical dosage forms using singal run.	HPLC	Orthophosphoricacid:ethanol (85:15 v/v) Flow rate: 1.0ml/min	Kinetex C ₁₈ Column (100 X 4.6mm) 2.6µm	RT: CPM:6.446 min LCF:4.749 min DXM: 3.374 min DEX: 2.135 min 230nm	20

1. UV Spectroscopic Method:

UV Spectroscopy is a commonly used analytical method for the quantitative analysis of compound. It is a powerful analytical technique for the determination of optical properties such as absorbance, reflectance, and transmittance. A simple, precise, and economical spectrophotometric method for the estimation of chlorpheniramine maleate in pharmaceutical bulk and tablet dosage form was developed and

validated. Various methods like simultaneous estimation, Q-absorption ratio, dual wavelength and derivative methods are used for the determination of chlorpheniramine alone or in combination with other drugs in marketed formulation. The given table describes the different spectroscopic method with the method description and conditions which are reported on review literature.

Table No. 2 UV Spectroscopic Method of Chlorpheniramine maleate:

Sr No.	Title	Method	Wavelength for Chlorpheniramine Maleate	Wavelength for other drug	Solvents	Ref No.
1	Simultaneous estimation and validation of paracetamol, phenylephrine hydrochloride, and chlorpheniramine maleate in tablet by	Simultaneous estimation and validation UV Spectrophotometric method	222.4nm	Paracetamol: 256.8nm Phenylephrine HCL: 236.8nm	0.1N NaoH	1

	spectrophotometric method					
2	Method development and validation of UV spectroscopic method for simultaneous estimation of chlorpheniramine maleate, and Diethylcarbamazine citrate in combined tablet Dosage forms	Development and validation of UV spectroscopic method	261nm	Diethylcarbamazine citrate:216nm	0.1N NaoH	2

CONCLUSION:

The review delineates the reported Spectroscopic and Chromatographic methods developed and validated for the estimation of Anti-Histamine drug Chlorpheniramine maleate. According to this review, it is concluded that different spectroscopic and chromatographic method are available for singal components as well as for combination UV and RP-HPLC method were found to be the most commonly used analytical methods.

REFERENCES

1. R. Sawant, R.Joshi, P.Lanke, L.Bhangale, Simultaneous Estimation and Validation of Paracetamol, Phenylephrine Hydrochloride, and Chlorpheniramine maleate in tablet by spectrophotometric method, Asian Journal of Pharmaceutical Research and Health care, Vol 3, No. 2 (2011), 23-28.
2. Gouru Santhosh Reddy, DaravathBhaskar, kamarapu s. k., method development and validation of UV Spectroscopic method for siultaneous estimation of chlorpheniramine maleate and Diethylcarbamazine citrate in combined tablet Dosage forms, International Journal of Pharmacy and Biological Sciences, Vol 3,2013, 216-223.
3. Maithani M, Raturi R, Gautam V, Kumar D, ChaudhariA,Gaurav A et al. Development and validation of RP-HPLCmethod for determination of chlorpheniramine and phenylephrine in pharmaceutical dosage form. PharmacieGlobale International journal of comprihensive pharmacy. 2010; 5(5):1-4, ISSN 0997-8157.
4. DaravathBhaskar, Reddy G.S., Kamarapu S.K., Development and Validation of RP-HPLC Method for Simultaneous Estimation of Clorpheniramine maleate and Diethylcarbamazine citrate in pharmaceutical dosage form, Asian Journal of Pharmaceutical and Clinical Research, Vol 7,2014, ISSN 0974-2441.
5. A.P. Dewani, B.B. Barik, V.D. Chipade, R.L. Bakal, A.V.Chandewar,S.K.Kanugo, RP-HPLC-DAD method for the determination of phenylepherine, paracetamol, caffieien and chlorpheniramine in bulk and marketed formulation, Arabian Journal of Chemistry, (2012).
6. AkwasiAcheampong, Wifredowusu Gyasi, GodfredDarko, Joseph Apau and Sylvester AddaiArhin, Validated RP-HPLC method for simultaneous determination and Quantification of Chlorpheniramine maleate, Paracetamol, and caffeine in tablet formulation, springer plus 5(1),2016, 1-8.
7. Darryl J. Hood, H. Y. Cheung, A chromatographic method for rapid and simultaneous analysis of codeine phosphate, ephedrine HCL and Chlorpheniramine maleate in cough- cold syrup formulation, Journal of Pharmaceutical and Biomedical Analysis 30 (2003) page no. 1595-1601.

8. OzenPiol, Murat Sukuroglu and Tuncelozden, Simultaneous Determination of Paracetamol, Phenylephrine Hydrochloride, Oxolamine citrate and Chlorpheniramine maleate by HPLC in Pharmaceutical Dosage Forms, *E-Journal of Chemistry* 2011,8(3),1275-1279.
9. Maria A. Moyano, Maria A. Rosasco, Maria T. Pizzorno, Adriana I. segall, Simultaneous Determination of chlorpheniramine maleate, Dexamethasone in a tablet Dosage form By Liquid Chromatography, *Drug Cosmetics, Forensic sciences, Journal of AOAC International* Vol.88, No.6, 1677-1678.
10. A. Ali, M. Ahmed, T. Mahmud, M.A. Qadir, K.Nadeem, A. Saleem, Stability-indicating high performance liquid chromatography method for simultaneous determination of Aminophylline and Chlorpheniramine maleate in pharmaceutical formulation, *Indian Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences*, 77 (5), 515, 2015.
11. K. Nalini, P. Narmada, G. VijayaLakhmi, Y. Gowtham and K.V. Jogi, Simultaneous Estimation of Paracetamol, Guaiphensin, Phenylephrine Hydrochloride, Chlorpheniramine maleate, Bromohexine Hydrochloride in combined tablet Dosage form by RP-HPLC, *International Journal Pharmaceutical Sciences and Research*, 2014, Vol-5 (2), 410-416.
12. Ramakrishna Kommanaand PraveenBasappa, Validated stability indicating RP-HPLC Method for Simultaneous Estimation of Codeine Phosphate and Chlorpheniramine maleate from their combined liquid dosage form, *Chromatography Research International*, Vol 7, 2013.
13. Ashok kumar, Rishabsharma, Anroop Nair and GautamSainf, Development and Validation of RP-HPLC method for simultaneous estimation of Nimesulide, Phenylephrine Hydrochloride, Chlorpheniramine maleate and Caffeine Anhydrous in Pharmaceutical Dosage form, *ActaPoloniaePharmaceutica-Drug Research*, Vol.69,2012, P.P 1017-1022.
14. A.R. Magesh, M.D.Dhanaraju, Development and Validation of RP-HPLC method for simultaneous estimation of Diethylcarbamazine citrate, Chlorpheniramine maleate, in Pharmaceutical preparations, *Chemical Science Transactions* 6, 2017, 316-322.
15. BlessySirigiri, PrasanthiChengalva, S. AngalaParameswari G. Aruna, A Novel HPLC method for the simultaneous determination of Chlorpheniramine maleate and Dextromethorphan in bulk and pharmaceutical formulation, *International Journal of Pharmaceutical Science and Rrsearch*, 9, 2018, 1147-1151.
16. Pinak M. Sanchaniya, Falgun A. Mehta, and Nirvi B. Uchadadiya, Development and Validation of an RP-HPLC method estimation of chlorpheniramine maleate, Ibuprofen and phenylephrine hydrochloride in combined pharmaceutical dosage form, *Chromatography Research Internation* Volume 2013, (6).
17. SravyaNeeli, Shanta Kumarikatakam, Stability indicating RP-HPLC method development and validation of paracetamol, Guaifenesin, Ambroxol Hydrochloride, Phenylephrine Hydrochloride, and Chlorpheniraminemaleate in bulk and combined dosage form, *World Journal of Pharmaceutical Research*, Vol 3, Issue 9, 1215-1232, ISSN-2277-7105.
18. Vishal Jain, Mukesh C. Sharma, Validated RP-HPLC Method for determining the levels of Bromhexine Hydrochloride, Chlorpheniramine maleate,

- Dextromethorphan HBrand Guaiphenesin in their Pharmaceutical dosage form, *Journal of Taibah University for Science* 10(1), 38-45, 2016.
19. Hamid Senyuva, TuncelOzzden, Simultaneous High Performance Liquid Chromatography Determination of Paracetamol, Phenylephrine Hydrochloride and Chlorpheniramine maleate in pharmaceutical dosage form, *Journal of Chromatography Science*, Vol.40, 2002.
 20. Zeinab Adel Nasr, Marwa M. soliman, Ekram H. Mohamed Fatma A. Fouad, Assesment of the greenness of micellar HPLC method for rapid separation and simultaneous estimation of chlorpheniramine maleate in presence of some co-administered drug in three pharmaceutical dosage forms using singal run, *ActaChromatographica*, 34(2), 138-149, 2021.
 21. Beckett AH, Stanlake JB. *Practical Pharmaceutical Chemistry*. 4th Edition, CBS Publishers and distributors, India, 1997; 2:93-98.
 22. Menddham J, Denney RC, Barnes JD, Thomas JK. *Vogel's textbook of Quantative Chemical Analysis*. 6th Edition, Dorling KinderslayPvt Ltd. India, 2006, 289-298.
 23. *British Pharmacopeia*, Vol. 1, HMSO, London, 1993, pp: 441-442.
 24. S. Wold, *J. Pharm. Biomed. Anal.*, 9(8), 589-596 (1991)
 25. ICH, Q2B, *Validation of Analytical Procedures: Methodology*, International Conference on Harmonization, Geneva, November 1996,1-8.
 26. Palabiyik, I.M., Onur, F., Multivariate optimization and validation of a capillary electrophoresis method for the simultaneous determination of dextromethorphan hydrobromur, phenylephrine hydrochloride, paracetamol and chlorpheniramine maleate in a pharmaceutical preparation using response surface methodology. *Anal. Sci.* 26 (8), 2010. page no. 853–859.
 27. [Www Google.Com](http://www.google.com).
 28. National Toxicological Program, Institute of Enviromental Health Science, National Institute of Health (NTP). 1992. *National Toxicology Program Chemical Repository Database*. Research Triangle Park, North Carolina

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